

1 **Syt2 and Syt7 function in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
8 synaptotagmins Syt2 and Syt7 as a lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating
9 factors in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

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